

Challenges to National Action Plan's Effectiveness in Countering Terrorism

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ABSTRACT: This research critically examines the impact and implementation of Pakistan's National Action Plan (NAP) initiated in response to the pervasive threat of terrorism. The study delves into the multifaceted causes of terrorism, exploring the evolution of the NAP from its inception in 2014 to the present. Special attention is given to the establishment of special trial courts, the revitalization of the National Counter Terrorism Authority (NACTA), and the envisioned Joint Intelligence Directorate (JID). This research scrutinizes the effectiveness of NAP's measures to counter terrorism financing, including the formation of a National Task Force and regulatory initiatives in banking. It also evaluates progress in monitoring religious seminaries and the blocking of unregistered SIMs.

However, challenges in the NAP's implementation, budgetary allocations, and ownership disputes among federal and provincial authorities are explored. The research concludes by emphasizing the need for strategic modifications in the NAP to address evolving security challenges in the context of hybrid warfare.

This research provides a concise yet comprehensive overview of the research study, summarizing its objectives, methodology, key findings, and implications.

Keywords: National Action Plan, Counter Terrorism, Security.

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1. Introduction

Terrorism has the potential to destabilize governments, ruin civil societies, paralyzed peace and security, and menace social and economic development. These factors collectively have a significant impact on the enjoyment of human rights. The safety of individuals represents a fundamental human right, and accordingly, it becomes a primary obligation of government authorities. Consequently, states are obligated to safeguard the human rights of their citizens and others by proactively taking measures to protect them from terrorist threats and bring those involved in planning or executing such acts to justice.

Pakistan has been grappling with terrorism for the past two decades. The main catalysts behind terrorism in Pakistan are often attributed to the aftermath of the 9/11 incident, the war in Afghanistan, and the country's unstable political landscape. Given these circumstances, a growing consensus appeared on the need for a comprehensive national response to tackle terrorism. This unanimity became particularly evident after the tragic attack on the Army Public School on December 16, 2014, which claimed the lives of many children. Consequently, the Pakistani parliament approved a 20-point National Action Plan (NAP) on December 24, 2014, which was drafted by the National Counter Terrorism Authority (NACTA) and the Interior Ministry. (Ali, Sh. 2021)

Over time, the conceptualization of NAP evolved to adapt to changing internal and external threat dynamics. Subsequent evaluations of its execution resulted in the development of an updated draft of NAP in 2021, which featured 14 points. This revision involved introducing new goals while removing some old objectives to ensure that efforts were continually reassessed.

The effectiveness of NAP can be categorized into two tiers, depending on the nature and urgency of the targets. Since the launch of NAP, 415 cases have been swiftly treated, according to NACTA. (Ali, Sh. 2021).

One of NAP's aims was to restore NACTA, and in 2020, NACTA was placed under the Ministry of Interior as an independent department following amendments in the NACTA act. A budget of Rs.248 million was allocated in 2019/20 to meet NACTA's human resource requirements. (NACTA Website, Jan 2024)

Recognizing the influence of social media on people's lives, NACTA launched operations like Tatheer and Chaukas, enabling Pakistani citizens to report terrorist activities on social media to the relevant authorities. Additionally, the successful conclusion of the Karachi operation significantly reduced terrorist activities by 98% in 2019, leading to a decrease in terrorism-related incidents from 482 in 2019 to 319 in 2020. (NACTA Website Jan 2024)

NACTA's initiatives have also resulted in several achievements, such as rationalizing individuals on the 4th Schedule of the Anti-Terrorism Act (ATA) and the establishment of a framework for taking legal action against these individuals. Furthermore, the Ministry of Interior designated 79 organizations and splinter outfits as banned under the ATA. (NACTA website Jan 2024)

Efforts to regulate and monitor seminaries were also made with the Directorate General of Religious Education registered over 5,000 seminaries nationwide. Collaboration with Ittehad-e-Tanzeem-ul-Madaris Pakistan (ITMP) facilitated the geo-trailing of madrasas in Punjab and Sindh. Moreover, measures to control terrorists' communication networks were implemented, including the verification of SIM cards through a biometric system, enhancing security and transparency.

In addressing the financing of terrorist organizations, Pakistan established a National Task Force on Suffocating Terrorism Financing, ensuring strict regulation of branchless/internet banking, and setting up Counter-Terrorism Financing Units (CFT) in

provincial Counter-Terrorism Departments. Surveillance of persons and funds listed under the Fourth Schedule of the ATA of 1997 was initiated to combat money laundering and terrorist financing. Furthermore, efforts to tackle Hawala/Hundi cases led to numerous detentions and substantial recoveries. (Khan, A. 2019)

While the progress achieved through NAP is commendable, the evolving security landscape in Pakistan may necessitate adaptations. Implementing the proposed NAP in 2021 will require the establishment of a new secretariat, headed by a competent person, to efficiently address counter-terrorism activities. NACTA, as an experienced and well-equipped body, appears poised to execute the proposed NAP 2021, which features distinct departments and a budget to support both soft and hard objectives.

Statement of the Problem

Terrorism remains a pressing global security concern, posing significant threats to the safety and stability of nations and their citizens. Pakistan has been remained victim of terrorism from last two decades, and this is one of hurdles in the way of development. To counter terrorism National Action Plan was designed. The NAP was comprehensive policy frameworks designed to eliminate terrorism within the country borders. Initially it gained some fruitful results but it has drawbacks also and its achievements are less. (Ali, 2023)

This research focuses on evaluating the effectiveness and impact of the National Action Plan (NAP) that was implemented in Pakistan in 2014 to combat terrorism.

2. Analysis

National Counter Terrorism Authority (NACTA) Aim and Effectiveness

The National Counter Terrorism Authority (NACTA) in Pakistan was established in 2009 with the aim of coordinating and integrating efforts to counter terrorism and extremism. However, NACTA's purpose has faced several challenges, leading to limited achievements. Here are some key reasons:

1. **Lack of Political Will:** NACTA has faced challenges in terms of political will and commitment from successive governments. The authority has often been under-resourced and lacked the necessary support and prioritization from the political leadership to effectively carry out its mandate.

2. **Bureaucratic Hurdles:** NACTA has struggled with bureaucratic hurdles and inter-agency coordination issues. Different government agencies and departments have their own priorities and often operate in silos, making it difficult for NACTA to coordinate and integrate counterterrorism efforts effectively.

3. **Limited Autonomy:** NACTA's effectiveness has been hampered by its limited autonomy and decision-making authority. It has often been overshadowed by other powerful institutions and agencies in Pakistan's security apparatus, which have their own agendas and priorities.

4. **Resource Constraints:** NACTA has faced significant resource constraints, including budgetary limitations and a lack of skilled personnel. This has hindered its ability to carry out its functions effectively, including intelligence gathering, analysis, and counterterrorism operations.

5. **Political Interference:** Political interference has also been a challenge for NACTA. The authority has faced pressure to prioritize certain issues or individuals based on political considerations, which can undermine its impartiality and effectiveness in countering terrorism.

6. **Complex Security Environment:** Pakistan's complex security environment, with various militant groups operating within its borders and in the region, has posed significant challenges to NACTA. The ever-evolving nature of terrorism and extremism requires continuous adaptation and proactive measures, which can be difficult to achieve in such an environment.

It is important to note that despite these challenges, NACTA has also made some progress in terms of developing strategies, conducting research, and enhancing coordination among different stakeholders. However, to fully achieve its purpose, NACTA requires consistent political support, increased resources, enhanced autonomy, and improved inter-agency coordination. (Noreen, 15 Sep 2023)

The effectiveness of the National Action Plan (NAP) can be gauged by examining post-NAP crime rates and the decrease in terrorist activities. NACTA (National Counter Terrorism Authority) asserts significant achievements in apprehending and eliminating individuals involved in terrorism. Nevertheless, Pakistan still faces considerable challenges on its path to becoming a truly secure and safe nation with respect to terrorism. (Rehman, K. 25 Oct 2023)

The National Counter Terrorism Authority (NACTA) in Pakistan was formulated with the aim of coordinating and implementing efforts to counter terrorism and ensure internal peace. Its creation was part of the National Action Plan (NAP) formulated in the aftermath of the tragic Army Public School attack in 2014. NACTA was envisioned as a central body to coordinate intelligence gathering and operations against terrorist groups, as well as to address the root causes of extremism. However, the effectiveness of NACTA has been a subject of debate, with some critics pointing to challenges in its operational capacity, coordination issues among various agencies, and the need for sustained efforts to address the underlying factors contributing to extremism. While NACTA has made certain contributions, there is ongoing scrutiny and discussion about the extent to which it has achieved its intended goals in ensuring internal peace and countering terrorism. (Khan, U. 26 Oct 2023)

3. National Action Plan: Objectives

After the tragic Army Public School (APS) attack in 2014, both the civilian and military leaders collaborated on a 20-point plan called the National Action Plan (NAP). The aim was to eliminate terrorism from the country and prevent any recurrence of such a

devastating incident. Essentially, it was an initiative focused on countering terrorism and ensuring the nation's security. (Rehman, K. 25 Oct 2023)

The National Action Plan (NAP) was a comprehensive strategy to counter terrorism and extremism. The primary aim of the NAP was to address the root causes of terrorism, strengthen security measures, and promote national cohesion. Some key objectives of the NAP included: (PILDAT, 2017)

1. Counterterrorism Measures: The NAP aimed to enhance law enforcement and intelligence capabilities to effectively counter terrorist activities. It called for the establishment of military courts to expedite the prosecution of terrorism-related cases, the establishment of special counterterrorism forces, and the strengthening of the legal framework to curb financing for terrorist organizations.

2. De-radicalization and Counter Extremism: The NAP emphasized the need for de-radicalization programs and initiatives to counter extremist ideologies. It aimed to promote a narrative of peace, tolerance, and moderation and to counter hate speech and extremist propaganda. The plan also called for the regulation of religious seminaries to prevent their misuse for radicalization purposes.

3. Border Management and International Cooperation: The NAP recognized the importance of effective border management to prevent the movement of terrorists across borders. It emphasized the need for enhanced coordination and intelligence sharing with neighboring countries, particularly Afghanistan, to address cross-border militancy and terrorism.

4. Measures against Hate Speech and Sectarian Violence: The NAP aimed to curb hate speech, incitement to violence and sectarian violence. It called for strict action against individuals and groups spreading hatred or inciting violence on the basis of religion, sect, or ethnicity. The plan also focused on promoting interfaith harmony and tolerance.

5. Economic Development and Governance Reforms: The NAP recognized the importance of socio-economic development and good governance in countering terrorism. It aimed to address issues of poverty, unemployment, and marginalization, which are often exploited by extremist groups. The plan also emphasized the need for reforms in the criminal justice system and the police to ensure effective implementation of counterterrorism measures.

It is must to know that the effectiveness and execution of the NAP have been subject to various challenges, including political will, resource constraints, and coordination issues. While progress has been made in certain areas, the full realization of the NAP's objectives remains a work in progress (Noreen, 15 Sep 2023)

Some key elements of the national action plan included the establishment of military courts for speedy trials of terrorists, the revival of the death penalty for those convicted of terrorism, and measures to curb hate speech and extremist literature. Additionally, the plan emphasized improved coordination among law enforcement agencies, intelligence agencies, and the military. The goal of the National Action Plan was to create a

comprehensive and coordinated approach to tackle terrorism and extremism at multiple levels ranging from military operations against militant groups to addressing the root causes of radicalization. While there were initial efforts to implement the plan, its effectiveness has been a subject of debate, with some critics pointing to challenges in its full and consistent implementation. (Khan, U. 26 Oct 2023)

4. National Action Plan: Need and Importance

The need for NAP arose due to several critical factors that required immediate attention and a coordinated response.

1. **Rising Extremism:** Pakistan had been witnessing a steady rise in extremist ideologies and activities within its borders. Militant groups, both domestic and foreign, were exploiting socio-political grievances, fostering radicalization, and carrying out acts of terror. The government recognized the urgency to address this growing menace.

2. **Security Concerns:** With an increase in terrorist attacks targeting civilians, security personnel, and important infrastructure, Pakistan faced significant security challenges. The NAP aimed to enhance the country's security apparatus, improve intelligence sharing, and strengthen law enforcement agencies to effectively combat terrorism.

3. **Public Opinion and Pressure:** The general public of Pakistan was increasingly concerned about the security situation and demanded decisive action from the government. There was a growing realization that a comprehensive and unified approach was needed to eliminate terrorism and protect the lives of citizens.

4. **International Obligations:** Pakistan faced international pressure to tackle terrorism effectively, as it had been a victim of various terrorist attacks in the past. The global community called for stronger measures and commitment from Pakistan to counter terrorism, as it posed a threat not only to the region but also to international peace and stability.

5. **Countering Radicalization:** Recognizing the importance of addressing the root causes of extremism, NAP incorporated strategies to counter radicalization and promote moderate, inclusive narratives. It aimed to promote social harmony, religious tolerance, and counter hate speech and extremist propaganda.

6. **Institutional Coordination:** The NAP recognized the need to enhance coordination among various law enforcement and intelligence agencies involved in counterterrorism operations. It aimed to establish an effective mechanism for information sharing, intelligence coordination, and joint operations against terrorist networks.

7. **Curtailling Terror Financing:** The NAP also focused on disrupting the financial networks that supported terrorist activities. It stressed the need to strengthen anti-money laundering measures, regulate charities and NGOs, and clamp down on illicit funding sources that sustained terrorist organizations.

Overall, the formation of the National Action Plan in Pakistan was a response to the urgent need to address the rising threat of terrorism and extremism. It aimed to create a comprehensive framework that encompassed security measures, counter-radicalization efforts, institutional coordination, and international cooperation to effectively combat terrorism within the country (Mehmood, 23 Sep 2023)

In the last few years, things have changed a lot in politics, money, and safety all around the world. There's hidden enemy causing trouble, making people upset. Pakistan has been hurt by two big problems: extreme thinking and terrorism. This happened mainly because of being a central part in the long wars in Afghanistan. The violence got worse when Pakistan became the main focus in the US-led war on terror. From June 2014, Pakistan started a strong effort called Zarb-e-Azb to kick out terrorists and their safe spots from tribal areas. Then, in December 2014, a really bad attack on APS happened, causing a lot of people to lose their lives. Because of this, top leaders decided to make the National Action Plan (NAP) to fight against terrorism in our society. (Khan I, 2023).

The Peshawar school attack shocked the nation and led to widespread outrage and grief. It served as a wake-up call for the Pakistani government and military to take decisive and coordinated action against terrorism and extremism. The incident exposed the severe threat posed by militant groups within Pakistan and highlighted the urgent need for a comprehensive strategy to address the root causes of terrorism, strengthen security measures, and improve coordination among various law enforcement and intelligence agencies. In the aftermath of the Peshawar attack, the political and military leadership recognized the gravity of the situation and acknowledged that a more robust and integrated approach was required. The National Action Plan was formulated as a response to this urgent need, outlining a 20-point agenda to address the multifaceted challenges posed by terrorism. The NAP aimed to demonstrate the government's commitment to eradicating terrorism and extremism, both through military operations against militant groups and by addressing issues such as radicalization, hate speech, and the financing of terrorism. While the plan was developed with a sense of urgency and purpose, its effective implementation faced challenges, and its success remains a subject of ongoing evaluation and debate. (Khan, U. 26 Oct 2023)

5. National Action Plan Implementation

Following are the challenges in the effective implementation of National Action Plan.

The role of the military and bureaucracy is slowing down the progress of national action plan. The tussle between the civilian government and the military in Pakistan, particularly regarding the execution of the National Action Plan (NAP), can be attributed to various factors. Some key causes include:

1. Civil-Military Relations: Pakistan has a history of complex civil-military relations, with periods of military rule interspersed with civilian governments. This historical dynamic can contribute to a lack of trust and cooperation between the civilian and military leadership.

2. **Divergent Priorities:** The civilian government and military may have divergent priorities and perspectives on how to address security issues and counterterrorism. This can lead to disagreements on the allocation of resources, the choice of strategies, and the pace of implementation of measures outlined in the NAP.

3. **Political Considerations:** The civilian government may perceive military involvement in domestic security affairs as encroaching on its authority. This perception can lead to resistance and friction, especially if there are suspicions of the military influencing political processes.

4. **Implementation Challenges:** The NAP involved a multi-faceted approach, addressing not only security measures but also issues such as education reform, countering extremism, and improving the criminal justice system. The complexity of these tasks and differences in approach between civilian and military authorities could contribute to challenges in effective implementation.

5. **Lack of Coordination:** Effective implementation of the NAP required seamless coordination between various law enforcement agencies, intelligence agencies, and the military. Any breakdown in communication or coordination could impede progress and create tensions.

6. **Public Perception:** The public perception of the roles and responsibilities of the civilian government and the military in addressing security challenges can also play a significant role. Negative public sentiment or criticism regarding the handling of security issues can further strain civil-military relations.

In summary, the tussle between civil and military authorities in Pakistan, particularly in the context of implementing the NAP, is a complex interplay of historical, institutional, and political factors that have contributed to challenges in achieving the intended goals of the National Action Plan. (Khan, U. 26 Oct 2023)

In Pakistan, there has always been a clear divide between civilian leaders, the military, and the bureaucracy since the country's beginning. Initially, civilian bureaucrats were in charge, but over time, military bureaucrats took over. The frequent imposition of Martial Law made this shift even more common, and during Musharraf's rule, it had a damaging impact on the country and its people. Musharraf proudly stated that all important positions in state institutions were given to military personnel, leaving no room for the public or their representatives to have a say in how the country is run. This power struggle continues today. The establishment of civil-military courts added to the frustration among civilian bureaucrats, as there was disagreement on how offenses should be punished and trials conducted. The military acting as a watchdog also undermines the essence of democracy. All of these factors have contributed to slowing down the progress of the National Action Plan. (Rehman, K. 25 Oct 2023)

The tussle between civilian and military authorities in Pakistan, particularly in the context of NAP, is a multifaceted issue driven by historical, institutional, and political factors. Divergent priorities, lack of coordination, and the public's perception of the roles of these stakeholders all contribute to challenges in achieving NAP's intended goals. Effective

communication, coordination, and a commitment to the plan's objectives are essential to overcome these obstacles.

6. Military Courts Formation and its Loopholes

The effectiveness of military courts in gaining their objectives can vary depending on the scenario and goals. Military courts are typically established to address cases involving military personnel and offenses related to the armed forces. Their objectives often include maintaining discipline, ensuring swift justice, and upholding military law. The success of these courts in achieving their objectives can depend on factors such as the fairness of proceedings, adherence to legal standards, and the perceived legitimacy of the court system. Public opinion, legal oversight, and the overall justice system also play roles in determining their effectiveness. (Noreen, 15 Sep 2023)

NAP bring military courts to existence, where the assurance of security was provided to the witnesses who give statements against terrorists. These military courts made their own analysis with help of other secret agencies upon which they make important decisions. Through different agencies they submit evidence on the basis of which the terrorists were convicted. In local courts no one want to provide witness because of fear of terrorists so this resulted in formation of military courts. (Khan, U. 26 Oct 2023)

The establishment of military courts in Pakistan was one of the key measures outlined in the National Action Plan (NAP) to address terrorism and insurgency more effectively. These courts were intended to expedite the trial and punishment of individuals involved in acts of terrorism. The rationale behind military courts was the need for swift and decisive justice to counter the rising threat of terrorism. The effectiveness of military courts in achieving their objectives has been a subject of debate and scrutiny. Proponents argue that military courts have led to quicker trials and convictions in terrorism cases, contributing to a more robust response against militants. They contend that the expedited judicial process is essential in dealing with the unique challenges posed by terrorism. On the other hand, critics raise concerns about issues related to due process, transparency, and accountability. There have been debates about the fairness of trials in military courts and the potential for human rights abuses. Critics also emphasize the importance of strengthening the civilian judicial system to handle terrorism cases effectively. The assessment of whether military courts have achieved their objectives depends on one's perspective and the criteria used for evaluation. While military courts may have expedited certain aspects of the legal process, broader questions remain about the overall impact on counterterrorism efforts, the protection of human rights, and the need for comprehensive judicial reforms. (Rehman, Sh. 4 Oct 2023)

Different people provide different insights into the objectives and achievements of military courts in Pakistan, particularly in the context of the National Action Plan (NAP) and the fight against terrorism. Their responses highlight various aspects of the role and effectiveness of military courts. They collectively present various facets of the role and effectiveness of military courts in Pakistan. While acknowledging the benefits of expediting trials and ensuring security for witnesses in terrorism cases, they also underscore concerns related to due process, transparency, and human rights. The effectiveness of military courts

is contingent on maintaining a balance between expediency and fairness, ensuring the protection of human rights, and strengthening the overall judicial system.

7. Tussle with Interior Ministry

The role of the Interior Ministry was indeed crucial in implementing and coordinating various aspects of the NAP. However, it is true that the effectiveness and involvement of the Interior Ministry in the NAP process have faced certain challenges. Some factors that may have contributed to the neglect or diminished role of the Interior Ministry include:

1. **Lack of Political Will:** The effectiveness of the Interior Ministry in implementing the NAP depends on the political will and support it receives from the government. If the political leadership does not prioritize the role of the ministry or provide it with the necessary resources and authority, its role may be diminished.

2. **Inter-Agency Coordination Issues:** Effective implementation of the NAP requires strong coordination among various government agencies and departments, including the Interior Ministry. However, coordination issues and bureaucratic hurdles among different agencies can hamper the ministry's ability to play a central role in the NAP process.

3. **Parallel Security Institutions:** Pakistan has multiple security institutions, including the military and intelligence agencies, which often have their own priorities and decision-making authority. This can sometimes overshadow the role of the Interior Ministry, limiting its involvement or effectiveness in implementing the NAP.

4. **Limited Resources and Capacity:** The Interior Ministry, like other government departments, may face resource constraints and a lack of skilled personnel, which can hinder its ability to effectively implement the NAP. Insufficient resources can limit the ministry's capacity to carry out its functions, such as intelligence gathering, law enforcement, and counterterrorism operations.

5. **Political Interference:** Political interference can also impact the role of the Interior Ministry in implementing the NAP. If political considerations or interference influence decision-making within the ministry, it can undermine its impartiality and effectiveness in countering terrorism and extremism.

It is important to note that while the role of the Interior Ministry may have faced challenges, the implementation of the NAP required collective efforts from various stakeholders, including security agencies, law enforcement agencies, provincial governments, and civil society. The success of the NAP depends on the effective coordination and collaboration of all relevant entities, including the Interior Ministry. (Noreen, 15 Sep 2023)

Different analysts provide a valuable analysis of the challenges Interior Ministry is facing in the implementation of the NAP. It emphasizes the intricate interplay of political will, inter-agency coordination, resource availability, and political interference in shaping the ministry's effectiveness. To address these challenges, comprehensive reforms and enhanced collaboration among various stakeholders are necessary to ensure the successful execution of the NAP.

8. Achievements of National Action Plan:

It is said by different analyst that progress has been made in some areas through NAP. It is essential to note that the implementation and effectiveness of NAP initiative have been subject to debate and varied outcomes.

Some of the achievements of the National Action Plan in Pakistan include:

1. **Crackdown on Militant Groups:** One of the primary objectives of the NAP was to eliminate militant organizations and their networks operating within Pakistan's borders. As a result, several military operations, such as Operation Zarb-e-Azb and Operation Radd-ul-Fasaad, were conducted, targeting terrorist hideouts and dismantling their infrastructure.

2. **Counterterrorism Legislation:** The Pakistani government introduced and implemented legislation to strengthen legal frameworks against terrorism. This included amendments to existing laws, such as the Anti-Terrorism Act, to facilitate the prosecution and sentencing of individuals involved in terrorist activities.

3. **Boosting Intelligence Agencies:** The NAP aimed to improve intelligence-gathering capabilities and coordination among various intelligence agencies. Efforts were made to enhance information sharing, improve surveillance techniques, and enhance overall counterterrorism intelligence.

4. **Madrasa Reforms:** The NAP sought to regulate religious seminaries (madrasas) to prevent their misuse for extremist indoctrination. Steps were taken to register madrasas, link their curriculum with mainstream education, and ensure transparency in their funding sources.

5. **Border Management:** Strengthening border security was a key component of the NAP. Measures were implemented to improve surveillance along the borders and curb illegal cross-border movement, which was often exploited by terrorist elements.

However, it is important to note that challenges and criticism remains regarding the implementation of the NAP. These include issues of coordination among various institutions, lack of financial resources, inconsistent progress, and concerns regarding the protection of human rights. Furthermore, eradicating extremism and terrorism is a long-term endeavor that requires sustained efforts, comprehensive strategies, and addressing underlying socioeconomic factors that contribute to radicalization.

Overall, while the NAP has seen some progress in certain areas, its success in achieving long-term security and stability in Pakistan is an ongoing process that necessitates sustained commitment and comprehensive efforts across multiple domains. (Mehmood, 23 Sep 2023)

The achievement of objectives in a national action plan depends on various factors, including the specific goals of the plan, the resources allocated, the effectiveness of implementation, and the prevailing circumstances. National action plans can be developed for a wide range of purposes, such as counterterrorism, economic development, healthcare, education, environmental protection, and much more. The success of national action plan

can be measured by assessing whether its intended goals were met, whether progress was made toward the desired outcomes, and whether the plan's initiatives had a positive impact on the intended areas. (Noreen, 15 Sep 2023)

The role of NACTA in achievements of NAP was to carry out research on topics relevant to terrorism and extremism and prepare and to circulate documents with international entities for facilitating cooperation in areas related to terrorism and to review laws and suggest amendments to the federal govt. so under the light of these points to an extent the objectives of the NAP have been achieved concluding the Karachi operation is a success of NAP to root out terrorist activities in the concerned areas. After the Karachi operation, terrorist activities fall down to 98% by 2019 from 2007-8. The terrorist incidents in Pakistan has decreased to 319 in 2020 from 482 in 2019. It is also a fact that the 100% objectives of NAP were not totally achieved. There are still exist some obstacle especially a sound consensus between civil and military bureaucracy within and military and international entities at large scale. Pakistan will take a long time to become a safe country. (Rehman, K. 25 Oct 2023)

The effectiveness of NAP in achieving its objectives has been a subject of ongoing debate and opinions on its success vary. Here are some key aspects:

1. **Security Measures:** NAP included measures such as the establishment of military courts, increased intelligence coordination, and military operations against militants. While there have been successes in certain operations and challenges but security threats persist.

2. **Counterterrorism Legislation:** The plan aimed at introducing and amending legislation to strengthen the legal framework for countering terrorism. Some legislative measures were implemented, including the revival of the death penalty for terrorism-related offenses.

3. **Combating Hate Speech and Extremism:** NAP highlighted the need to counter hate speech and extremist ideologies. Efforts were made to regulate and monitor madrasas (religious schools) to prevent the spread of radical ideologies. However, the effectiveness of these measures is debated.

4. **Financial Action against Terrorism:** The plan included steps to curb the financing of terrorism. Pakistan has made efforts to comply with international standards on countering money laundering and terror financing, but challenges persist.

5. **Education Reforms:** NAP emphasized the importance of educational reforms to counter extremism. Efforts were made to revise textbooks and promote a more tolerant curriculum, but progress has been slow.

6. **Return of Afghan Refugees:** The plan called for the repatriation of Afghan refugees as a security measure. However, challenges in repatriation and concerns about human rights have complicated this aspect. While there have been some achievements, the overall success of NAP is debated, and challenges remain. Factors such as political will, coordination among various stakeholders, and addressing the root causes of extremism

contribute to the complexity of evaluating the plan's success. The effectiveness of NAP is an ongoing and evolving matter in the context of Pakistan's efforts to counter terrorism and ensure internal peace. (Khan, N. M. 25 Oct 2023)

This analysis offer insights into the achievements of the National Action Plan in Pakistan, highlighting successes in various areas while also acknowledging persistent challenges. This provide a balanced and informative assessment of the NAP's effectiveness and the complexity of addressing terrorism and extremism in the region.

9. Conclusion

This research illuminates the complexities surrounding Pakistan's response to the tragic Peshawar Army Public School attack and the subsequent implementation of the National Action Plan (NAP). While the NAP displayed positive aspects in its comprehensive approach, increased military operations, revival of military courts, and crackdown on terrorist financing. It faced challenges and criticisms, particularly in terms of lackluster implementation, civil-military coordination issues, and concerns about due process.

The role of secret agencies, including the Special Branch and Intelligence Bureau, emerged as pivotal in gathering intelligence, assessing threats, supporting law enforcement, and contributing to counter-terrorism policies. However, the effectiveness of these agencies was contingent upon cooperation with other government departments, law enforcement agencies, and the judiciary.

Moving forward, recommendations emphasize transitioning to civilian leadership, strengthening provincial mechanisms, developing monitoring and evaluation systems, reforming the criminal justice system, and empowering the National Counter Terrorism Authority (NACTA). Future suggestions include adopting a holistic national strategy, strategically implementing NAP points, enhancing capabilities, streamlining monitoring committees, establishing a counter-narrative, providing oversight through the National Security Council, periodic NAP revision, and embracing a comprehensive counterterrorism perspective.

In conclusion, the challenge lies not only in responding to immediate security threats but also in addressing the deep-rooted social, economic, and ideological factors contributing to extremism. The success of counter-terrorism efforts in Pakistan requires sustained commitment, collaboration, and adaptability to effectively navigate the evolving landscape of insecurity, terrorist violence, and extremism.

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